

From Intellectual Foundations of the Self-Sufficiency Policy to Water Stress: An Analysis of Conditions in Iran

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Abstract:

Water scarcity in Iran has caused irreversible environmental damage, including the drying of Lake Urmia, water stress in 278 cities, and land subsidence affecting 24 million people. In addition, multi-hour water and electricity outages have become a daily phenomenon in the lives of Iranians. While previous studies attribute this crisis to agricultural expansion, unsustainable extraction, low productivity, managerial inefficiency, weak legislation, and poor governance, this research examines the deeper ideological roots in foundational thought. It focuses on the state-driven ideology of "self-sufficiency," centralized economic control, the rise of "rentier contractors," and the influence of Islamic socialism on Iran's economic and political structures. Furthermore, it investigates the impact of Marxist thought and Dependency Theory in shaping systemic patterns. Using documentary analysis and interdisciplinary interviews, the study explores the complex interplay of climatic, economic, political, philosophical, and historical factors. The findings reveal that Islamic socialism provides the foundation for the dominance of Dependency Theory, reinforces the rhetoric of self-sufficiency and state economic control, and thus plays a key role in sustaining Iran's persistent water crisis.

Keywords: *Water crisis; Iran; Food self-sufficiency; Rentier contractors; Dependency Theory; Islamic leftist ideology; Marxism.*

Introduction

Water has always been a vital concern for Iranians. The excavation of 21,000 kilometers of qanats, designated as UNESCO World Heritage sites, the construction of local water structures, and climate-adapted agricultural practices are examples of ancient Iranian efforts to survive, adapt, and manage limited water resources over thousands of years (Daoudy, Sowers, and Weinthal 2022; Hejazi 2023; Saatsaz and Rezaei 2023)

In recent decades, with the introduction of technologies for drilling deep and semi-deep wells, coupled with an emphasis on food self-sufficiency, uncontrolled dam construction, and the establishment of heavy industries and water-intensive projects in prohibited plains, Iran's traditional water resource management system has undergone fundamental changes, leading to a significant increase in water consumption. Currently, 278 cities and 56% of Iran's population are under water stress, and 23 million people are at risk of ground subsidence (Behling et al. 2022;

Center n.d.; Golian et al. 2021; Jalal Mirnezami, Molle, and Talebi Eskandari 2024; Rahimi-Feyzabad et al. 2022).

Many studies have pointed to the water crisis in Iran (Islami and Rahimi 2019; Mirzavand and Bagheri 2020). About 90% of renewable freshwater is utilized in Iran, indicating a high level of water stress in the country (Ketabchy 2021; Nouri et al. 2023). The Falkenmark Water Stress Index categorizes water conditions in a region into four categories based on annual per capita water availability: no stress (more than 1700 cubic meters per capita), stress (1000-1700 cubic meters per capita), scarcity (500-1000 cubic meters per capita), and absolute scarcity (<500 cubic meters per capita) (Brown and Matlock, 2017). Based on this index, Iran, with a renewable water availability of 1560 cubic meters per capita, falls within the category of water stress (Falkenmark, Lundqvist, and Widstrand 1989; Nouri et al. 2023).

In addition to environmental factors such as 85% of Iran's land area being in dry and semi-dry climates, low annual rainfall of one-third of the global average, and high evaporation rates up to three times the global average, many studies have been conducted on other causes of Iran's water crisis. The factors contributing to Iran's water problem include the expansion of agricultural lands, unsustainable water extraction, low water productivity, inefficiency and poor management, weak legislation, inadequate governance in the water sector, and unsustainable industrialization (Barati, Pour, and Sardooei 2023; Karimi et al. 2024; Nouri et al. 2023; Rastegaripour et al. 2024)

However, it appears that there are other factors beyond those mentioned that have laid the necessary groundwork for the formation of this crisis. Ideological foundations have influenced Iranian culture, literature, and intellectual thought for decades. The influence of leftist ideology from the Constitutional Revolution era (1905 AD) to the Islamic Revolution of 1979 has been significant. This influence manifested through the predominance of the "Dependency Theory" during the early years of the Islamic Revolution and in formulating the constitution under the slogans of self-sufficiency and state control over the economy (Pesaran 1982). A literature review on this topic reveals a lack of attention to addressing the water crisis from an ideological standpoint to the extent that it has been overlooked in earlier research.

Therefore, this paper aims to analyze the water crisis in Iran from the perspective of the dominant ideologies of "self-sufficiency" and "state control over the economy." It also aims to explore the roots and introduce a phenomenon called "Rentier Contractors," while examining the influences of "Marxist ideology" and "Dependency Theory," which have provided the necessary framework for the emergence of this crisis. The paper seeks to answer fundamental questions about how, despite environmental constraints, the slogans of self-sufficiency and agricultural development were incorporated into the text of the constitution, and what factor or factors laid the groundwork for the widespread dam construction and establishment of water-intensive industries in prohibited plains.

Theoretical Foundations

Ideological foundations play a crucial role in shaping legislation within legal systems. Ideological principles influence legal systems and governance, impacting the values, conventions, and beliefs that underpin laws and regulations, as well as the functioning of societies and interpersonal interactions. Understanding the ideological basis of legal systems is essential for grasping the rationale behind laws and their societal impacts. Therefore, by examining the ideological origins of legal frameworks, we can enhance our comprehension of the guiding principles for formulating and implementing laws within a particular society (Freeden 2000; Lichtheim 1965). Thus, several ideological factors that seem to have influenced the drafting of the Constitution within the specific circumstances of the revolution's success are examined.

- Socialism & Marxism

The term and concept of socialism have their origins in the early nineteenth century. However, there has been no universally accepted practical definition of socialism or the socialist economy. The theory of the socialist economy has not always been interchangeable with Marxism, as scholars before Marx have produced significant works and research on socialism. Socialism can be argued to predate Marx, starting with the French Revolution in 1789 and culminating with the publication of Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels' famous Manifesto in 1848 (LOVELL 1992; Simkhovitch 1913).

Early socialists who pioneered neoclassical economics were critical of classical economists. The most significant of these complaints are:

- Private ownership should be replaced by a national commodity society, with public ownership taking its place.
- Working is a public and universal duty; however, not every factory worker follows the orders and directives of the highest authority, which are based on the social value concept.
- Decisions on the allocation of production and distribution resources are centralized.
- Individual consumer items should be divided among members according to the concept of equality, as there is no money or wages.
- The government is responsible for all economic matters, and all economic transactions are conducted by the government (Anon 2020; Rowthorn 1973).

In his book "Capital," Marx regards the state as a defender and preserver of the capitalist system; hence, he advocates for the complete collapse of the state and the elimination of private ownership. Marx proposes the concept of class to illustrate that politics is subordinate to economics (Luke 1999).

- The Spread of Leftist Thought in Iranian Literature and Culture

Regarding "the presentation of idealistic issues and attention to underprivileged classes, the activities of leftist parties and movements, global successes of Marxism in the Soviet Union, China, Vietnam, and other parts of the world, gaining legitimacy for supporters of Marxism due to their selflessness and self-sacrifice, presenting new themes in literature such as anti-dictatorship, freedom, and justice," Iran's Marxist literature flourished and thrived, as did elsewhere (Mosavi Borazgani and Mohammadi 2023).

The traditional and religious elites in Iran shared common ground with communist movements on issues such as justice, attention to impoverished groups, and the need to depose the Shah. They

embraced a more socialist interpretation of Islam. In this perspective, Dr. Shariati plays a significant role. Shariati, an "ideologue of the revolution," was considered the revolution's second figure after Ayatollah Khomeini, according to Michel Foucault. He attempted to bridge Marxism and Islam by transcending materialism and was successful in presenting an "Islamic left ideology" that integrated religion into an ideology. From 1968 to 1972, Shariati's lectures had a profound impact on young people, intellectuals, political currents, guerrilla groups, and revolutionaries, leading to the spread of anti-capitalist ideology throughout Iranian society. This set the stage for Dependency Theory to become dominant among revolutionaries (Ayoob 1981; Fadaee 2022; Pesaran 2008).

- Dependency Theory and Iran's Islamic Revolution

Dependency Theory has its roots in studies of the Third World, particularly Latin America (Brazil and Mexico). According to this theory, the relationship between Third World countries as dependent nations and advanced or metropolitan countries is purely economic and unequal, and it must be analyzed within the context of the global system. The political ideology that underpins Dependency Theory is Marxism. From the Dependency Theory approach, André Gunder Frank, Paul Baran, and Dos Santos emphasize colonial linkages between industrial countries (center) and third-world countries (satellites). They argue that underdevelopment is caused by colonial relationships, the Industrial Revolution, conflicts, and uneven commerce. Therefore, they advocate for breaking away from the global market and striving for independence and self-sufficiency (Ahumada and Torres 2024; Palestini 2023; Papoli-Yazdi and Ebrahimi 2009).

Another feature of Dependency Theory is absolving oneself of internal concerns and conflicts while blaming foreign (industrial) countries. This trait became dominant in the rhetoric of Iran's triumphant revolutionaries in February 1979. This anti-Western sentiment exacerbated the alienation that constitutional intellectuals had initiated by defining the concept of "homeland" as emphasizing Iranian thought and superiority, as well as "othering," which evolved from "anti-Arab and anti-Turk" sentiments during the constitutional period 1905 to "anti-West and anti-America" sentiments during the 1979 revolution (KAVEH PISHGHADAM 2010; Pesaran 2008; Shahidani and Penkovtsev 2017)

In the same context, the new constitution is also drafted, and under the influence of Marxist leftist views, the following Dependency Theory ideas are included in the constitution:

- Belief in a global fight against capitalism (the preamble of the constitution);
- Government control of the economy (Principles 43 and 44);
- Ensuring self-sufficiency in research, technology, industry, and agriculture (Principles 3 and 43)

(KAVEH PISHGHADAM 2010; Khalili 2009; Pesaran 2008).

As a result, the slogan of food self-sufficiency became the focal point of government planning, leading to an expansion of agricultural land. Furthermore, the size of the government increased dramatically, and Iran's economic system came under government control, which, coupled with oil rent, led to increased inefficiency and corruption at all levels. Influential individuals within the

government established networks of "supporter-follower" relationships to maintain the status quo and gain additional benefits. This form of corruption in government, where loyalty and commitment take precedence over individual expertise, is considered the worst form of corruption. This established the framework for a water crisis in Iran (Jamali Oskooi, BAKHSHAYESHI ARDESTANI, and BANIHASHEMI 2019; Matthee 2020; PANAHI and AMINI 2011; Rose-Ackerman and Palifka 2016; Saeidi 2001).

-Rentier Government and Rentier Contractors (Rent-Seeking Contractors)

Rentier regimes inherently take an unfair approach to distributing economic rents. In a rentier society, everyone benefits to some extent from economic rents. However, these benefits will vary significantly from person to person (Bina 1992). Given Iran's administrative institutions, this initiative was conceived and implemented using a top-down approach based on oil income. Rentier governments are economically and technically autonomous from their societies in their pursuit of economic rents, which separates them from their relevant individuals and leads to their social autonomy. As a result, such administrations do not see the necessity for different social strata to engage in planning processes. Communities do not play a substantial role in decision-making processes since the source of power (oil or other raw materials) is held underground, and governments have complete control over their use (Beck 2009; Torabi, Zabih., Rezvani, M. Reza. & Badri 2020).

Rentier contractors, born of government control over the economy, rentier government, and supporter-follower networks, have initiated many destructive projects under slogans such as self-sufficiency, poverty alleviation, job creation, and so on, all with a structural and unsustainable perspective. The implementation of these projects has led to government budget losses as well as environmental costs borne by individuals and the regional ecosystem (Harris 2013; Hosseini et al. 2020). Rentier contractors' activities include the post-revolutionary frenzy of dam construction, as well as the establishment of steel and petrochemical industries in restricted areas of the country (Figure 1)(Association n.d.; Ghazinoory, Fatemi, and Adab 2022).

153 of Iran's 172 operational national dams (89%) were built post-revolution. Many experts believe that reckless dam development, despite 60% of dam reservoirs being empty, is a significant cause of the country's marshes and lakes drying up (Manouchehri and Mahmoodian 2002; Rezazadeh 2020). Satellite photography reveals that, as dam construction increases in the Urmia Lake basin, the cultivated land area expands, whereas the water levels of Urmia Lake decline (Naboureh et al. 2021). However, Iran is still in the process of assessing the feasibility of constructing 340 new dams, which reflects the power and continuity of the activities of rent-seeking contractors (Madani 2014).

The Gotvand Dam, Iran's second-largest reservoir dam, exemplifies the influence of rentier contractors in Iranian dam construction projects. Despite initial concerns about faulty field research and inadequate assessments regarding the presence of a salt dome at the dam reservoir site, and the subsequent discovery of this incorrect placement after 30% of the project was completed, the project was ultimately finished. Consequently, this led to an increase in the salt level of the Karun River and significant environmental challenges in the region; to the point where

the then-head of Iran's Department of Environment referred to it as a "crime against Iran's environment. It is worth noting that the impacts of the Dependency Theory can also be observed in the construction of the Gotvand Dam: "Prior to the revolution, American experts assessed the environmental concerns of the dam and recommended building it 15 kilometers higher. However, in post-revolutionary evaluations, officials who re-examined the project claimed that the Americans had intended for the dam reservoir to be smaller and had misidentified its optimal location; consequently, the dam's location was altered, and it was decided to construct the dam at a new site" (Amiri et al. 2023; Jalali, Zarei, and Gutiérrez 2019; Qemashi 2016).

The influence of rentier contractors extends beyond dam construction; the development of 70% of highly water-intensive steel and petrochemical factories in sensitive and prohibited plains is another example of the activities of corrupt contractors in the country, which has exacerbated pressure on Iran's limited groundwater resources and necessitated the implementation of inter-basin water transfer projects to supply water for these industries, leading to widespread protests in Iran's central regions over the past few decades (Alfoneh 2022; Hosseiniebalam and Ghaffarparasad 2015; Naderi et al. 2024; Parvzimehr et al. 2020).

Figure 1: Spatial distribution map of steel and petrochemical factories in the country's plains

Source: Iran Renewable Energy Association

- Food self-sufficiency

Self-sufficiency is defined differently in economic literature. From one perspective, self-sufficiency involves producing all strategic products locally to meet the country's consumption levels. From another angle, a balance between exports and imports can indicate self-sufficiency. The primary objective of self-sufficiency is to attain relative independence in strategic products. In practice, self-sufficiency entails manufacturing each product in sufficient quantities to satisfy the country's overall domestic demand. Achieving self-sufficiency in strategic crops, such as wheat, a major food staple and one of the most critical agricultural products, has a significantly greater impact. Due to variations in climatic conditions, production resource utilization capabilities, economic development levels, and the international division of labor, only a limited number of countries have achieved absolute self-sufficiency in meeting all their food consumption needs. Under such circumstances, the expansion of commercial relations becomes inevitable. Consequently, self-sufficiency can be perceived as a developmental scenario in which non-substitutable imports are financed by exports that generate the necessary revenue to repay them (Clapp 2017; Maroufpoor et al. 2021).

Article 43 of the Constitution emphasizes that economic independence is essential for eliminating poverty and deprivation and fulfilling human needs during the growth period, while preserving freedom. The ninth paragraph of this article focuses on strengthening agricultural, livestock, and industrial production to meet public needs, thereby leading the country towards self-sufficiency and reducing dependence. Ayatollah Khomeini, the founder of the Islamic Republic of Iran, viewed the importation of food as a symbol of dependence on foreign powers and criticized the Shah's regime for impoverishing farmers and forcing them to migrate to cities. He extolled agriculture as the "sacred profession of the prophets," which ensures the independence of the country. This led to an increase in agricultural production from 17.8 million tons in 1977 to 120 million tons in 2017 (Behling et al. 2022; Haghayeghi 1990; Jalal Mirnezami et al. 2024; Nouri et al. 2023).

Despite 85% of Iran's land area being in arid and semi-arid climates, with an average precipitation of one-third of the global average and an evaporation rate three times the global average, the incorporation of self-sufficiency into Constitutional principles and its centralization has resulted in irreversible damage to Iran's environment and water resources (Behling et al. 2022; Karimi et al. 2024; Madani 2014).

Iran has a relatively low water efficiency; according to statistics, in 2024, the gross domestic product per unit of water usage was \$22 in Russia, \$26 in China, \$44 in the United States, \$28 in Sweden, \$17 in Turkey, and only \$5 in Iran (WORLD BANK GROUP n.d.)(Rastegaripour et al. 2024). The agricultural sector consumes approximately 90% of the country's water resources, with around 55% of this amount being drawn from subsurface sources (Maghrebi et al. 2020). By 2022, 410 out of the 609 surveyed plains in the country have reached critical conditions due to excessive water extraction. Over-extraction of groundwater resources has significantly increased the likelihood of land subsidence. Notably, the rate of land subsidence in Iran is more than five times the global average, putting approximately 8 million residential units and 24 million people at risk (Barati et al. 2023; Center n.d.; Rastegaripour et al. 2024).

Iran's climatic conditions, low water efficiency, agriculture's high share of the country's water consumption, and increased risk of land subsidence all highlight the inefficiency of the principle of self-sufficiency; however, agriculture and achieving food self-sufficiency remain emphasized by government officials.

- Food Security

Food security has evolved and can be influenced by various domestic and global issues. However, Iranian authorities define food security as self-sufficiency in agricultural food products, particularly wheat production. Nevertheless, self-sufficiency can only contribute to food security if it is consistent with comparative advantage and sustainable resource management. The results of a simultaneous examination of self-sufficiency and comparative advantage, as well as the actual impact of self-sufficiency on net social profits as a criterion for food security, revealed that although self-sufficiency policies, including price supports, input subsidies, credit subsidies, research programs, and promotional activities, led to increased physical productivity of wheat farms and an expansion of cultivated areas, the net social profits from wheat production during the study period were negative, indicating a negative impact of the self-sufficiency policy on food security (Bagher Ghalibaf, Gholami, and Mohammadian 2022; Clapp 2017; Maroufpoor et al. 2021; Najafi Alamdarlo, Riyahi, and Vakilpoor 2019).

Current realities in Iran also indicate a trend towards a water crisis, with manifestations such as the drying up of the Zayandeh Rud River, Lake Hamun, and Lake Urmia, critical water shortages in certain regions like the Birjand and Jiroft plains, and the country's per capita renewable water resources approaching a water crisis threshold. Despite three decades of national water supply policies aimed at achieving sustainable agriculture, current realities suggest that neither water management nor wheat production have followed a sustainable trajectory (Madani 2014).

Research Method:

This study employed a multi-method qualitative research design to examine the intellectual, ideological, and institutional foundations of Iran's water crisis. The research process unfolded in three interrelated stages, each contributing to the development and validation of an interdisciplinary conceptual framework.

Stage 1 – Development of the Theoretical Framework: An initial conceptual model was constructed through a systematic review of peer-reviewed academic literature, policy reports, and archival documents related to water governance, dependency theory, ideological statecraft, and state-centric development in Iran. The aim of this stage was to identify the historical and epistemological roots of the country's environmental degradation and policy failures (Figure 2).

Stage 2 – Expert Interviews and Model Refinement: To empirically support and revise the preliminary model, 28 hours of semi-structured, face-to-face interviews were conducted with 30 senior scholars and researchers in political science, philosophy, history, literature, social sciences, economics, environmental studies, and geography—primarily affiliated with the University of Tehran. Participants were selected through purposive sampling based on criteria such as academic rank, research output, and expertise in development, governance, and ideology. The interview data

were manually coded and thematically analyzed using an inductive approach. This process led to the identification of key themes, conceptual linkages, and causal relationships among variables, contributing to the revision and enhancement of the initial framework and the development of the final conceptual model. (Table 1,2)(Figure 3).

Stage 3 – Model Evaluation through Expert Survey: In the final stage, a structured questionnaire based on the revised conceptual model was distributed among the same 30 university professors from eight different faculties at the University of Tehran. The objective was to assess the perceived significance and interrelation of ideological, political, and economic factors in shaping the water crisis. Survey data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and logical reasoning to evaluate the internal coherence and explanatory power of the proposed causal pathways (Table 3).

This triangulated methodology—combining documentary analysis, expert interviews, and academic surveying—enabled the construction of a comprehensive and interdisciplinary model that interlinks ideological discourses, institutional dynamics, rent-seeking networks, and environmental mismanagement.

Figure 2. Initial concept
(Extracted from the results of studies conducted in various fields)

Table 1. Measuring the level of relationship and impact of each item in shaping the water crisis in the country

Statement	Effectiveness				
	Effectless	low effect	Somewhat effective	High impact	Quite effective
The permeation of Marxist ideals into Iran's culture and development literature					
The introduction and spread of Marxist ideology in Iranian literary literature					
Islamic left ideology (inspired by the ideas of Dr. Ali Shariati)					
Anti-capitalist and leftist ideas are spreading among citizens, elites, and intellectuals					
Expanding the activity of left parties in Iran					

Table 2. Characteristics of the academic community members participating in the second stage of the research

Faculty	Specialization area	Number of participants
Literature and Humanities	Philosophy	3
Literature and Humanities	Contemporary Iranian history	2
Literature and Humanities	Contemporary Iranian literature	3
Law and Political Science	Political thought - Iranian issues	4
Economics	Economic development	3
Social Sciences	Social development and planning	4
Geography	Rural sustainable development	5
Geography	Land management	4
Environment	Environment	2
Academic rank	Professor	7
	Associate Professor	13
	Assistant Professor	10
Gender	Male	27
	Female	3

Research findings

Following interviews with relevant academics, in addition to the leftist ideology, the "Iranian climate" and "oil income" were identified as key elements. The interplay between "government dominance over the economy" and "oil rentier government" was identified as a major factor in "inefficiency in management" and the formation of "supporter-follower networks" and "rentier contractors". Furthermore, "inefficiency in management" was recognized as a contributing factor

to low water productivity in Iran. Given that Iran's economy was characterized as a "state economy" in the first decade of the revolution and "state capitalism" in subsequent decades, the phrase "state domination over the economy" was incorporated into the final concept, encompassing both economic structures prevalent in Iran. The final concept also highlighted "Dependency Theory" as the intellectual foundation underlying the "Self-sufficiency slogan" and "government dominance over the economy" (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Final concept
(Extracted from the results of studies conducted in various fields and reviewed)

Table 3. Respondents' opinions on the impact of the mentioned factors on the intellectual and ideological roots of the water crisis in Iran

Statement	Number of responses	Very high	High	To some extent low	Low	Very low
Impact of "Left-wing ideology in Iran" on "Socialist interpretation of Islam" and "Anti-capitalist intellectual space of the 57 Revolution"	18	44.4%	44.4%	11.1%	-	-
Impact of "Socialist interpretation of Islam and Islamic left ideology" on "Anti-capitalist intellectual space of the 57 Revolution"	18	61.1%	38.9%	-	-	-
Impact of "Anti-capitalist intellectual space of the 57 Revolution" on the introduction of Dependency Theory (self-sufficiency and government control over the economy) into the Constitution	19	42.1%	52.6%	5.3%	-	-
Impact of "Economic principles of the Constitution" on "Government control over the economy and rentier government"	7	71.4%	28.6%	-	-	-
Impact of "oil" on "Rentier government"	7	85.7%	28.6%	-	-	-
Interaction between "Government control over the economy" and "Rentier government"	6	66.7%	33.3%	-	-	-
Impact of "Rentier government" on "Inefficiency in management"	6	83.3%	16.7%	-	-	-
Impact of "Inefficiency in management" on "Water crisis"	19	94.7%	5.3%	-	-	-
Impact of "Government control over the economy" and "Rentier government" on "Supporter-follower networks" and "Rentier contractors"	5	60%	40%	-	-	-
Impact of "Inefficiency in management", "Supporter-follower networks", and "Rentier contractors" on "Structural and unstable perspective"	5	60%	40%	-	-	-
Impact of "Structural and unstable perspective" on "Water crisis"	17	29.4%	52.9%	17.6%	-	-
Impact of "Self-sufficiency slogan" on "Unregulated water extraction"	19	21.1%	63.2%	10.5%	5.3%	-
Impact of "Inefficiency in management" on "Low water productivity"	18	83.3%	16.7%	-	-	-
Impact of "Unregulated water extraction and low water productivity" on "Water crisis"	15	53.3%	33.3%	13.3%	-	-
Impact of "Iran's climate" on "Water crisis"	15	28.6%	57.1%	14.3%	-	-

Causal Analysis of Ideological, Economic, and Environmental Dynamics in Post-Revolutionary Iran

This study presents a comprehensive causal model that elucidates the interplay between ideological origins, economic governance, and environmental outcomes in post-revolutionary Iran, with a particular focus on the water crisis. Using expert opinion gathered from 30 senior scholars in philosophy, contemporary history, political economy, sustainable development, and environmental studies, we analyzed a multi-layered structure of influences rooted in Iran's ideological transformation after the 1979 Revolution (Table 3)(Figure 3).

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that Iran's water crisis is not merely an environmental or climatic issue but a deeply rooted, multidimensional crisis embedded in the country's ideological, institutional, and economic structures. While previous research has primarily approached the water crisis from technical, managerial, and policy-making perspectives, this study investigates the underlying

ideological and intellectual foundations that have shaped destructive governance structures and misguided policies.

The causal chain traced in this research reveals the significant influence of leftist ideology and a socialist interpretation of Islam—particularly through the intellectual legacy of Dr. Ali Shariati—in shaping the anti-capitalist discourse of the 1979 Islamic Revolution. This discourse has been institutionalized in the Iranian Constitution through economic principles inspired by dependency theory, emphasizing resistance to global capitalism, state dominance over the economy, and a focus on national self-sufficiency in food production.

This ideological foundation, combined with Iran's dependence on oil revenues, has led to the formation of a rentier state. In this context, resource allocation is governed less by merit, efficiency, or market competition, and more by networks of rent distribution involving politically connected contractors and state-affiliated intermediaries. These actors have played a central role in the implementation of large-scale infrastructure projects—such as extensive dam construction, inter-basin water transfers, and expansion of irrigation schemes—often with devastating environmental consequences, including the degradation of water resources and destruction of aquatic ecosystems.

The most visible symbols of this ecological collapse are the drying of Lake Urmia and numerous other wetlands such as Gavkhouni, Bakhtegan, and Jazmourian. Additionally, ideologically driven policies like self-sufficiency in agriculture, pursued without regard for Iran's climatic limitations, have severely stressed water supplies. Agriculture still accounts for over 90% of water consumption in Iran, despite its low productivity and unsustainable water use.

Today, more than 278 cities in Iran are experiencing high water stress, and over 24 million people live in areas at serious risk of land subsidence due to groundwater depletion. These facts underscore the structural and ideological nature of the crisis. Ultimately, Iran's water crisis is the outcome of the convergence of unsuitable climatic conditions, state-dominated economic structures, rent-seeking networks, and ideological doctrines that prioritize state control and self-reliance over sustainability, efficiency, and adaptability.

Without a fundamental rethinking of these ideological foundations, constitutional economic principles, and decision-making structures, no lasting solution to the water crisis can be expected. The authors propose several measures to address this crisis and its underlying causes, including a revision of the Constitution; changes in overarching strategies and policies, such as reassessing the goal of achieving self-sufficiency; enhancing transparency in governmental structures and oil revenues; and replacing confrontation with the world with free trade and constructive engagement.

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